

Evidence for dry merger driven BCG growth in XXL-100-GC X-ray clusters

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on behalf of the XXL collaboration

Brightest cluster galaxies: Mass growth

- The growth of BCGs is closely related to the properties of their host clusters.
- BCGs form hierarchically via mergers.
- BCGs at $z < 1$ experience major mergers and have grown in mass by ~ 2 since $z \sim 1$ (e.g. Lidman+12).
- Does the dominant growth mechanism change at $z \sim 1$, with in situ SF dominating at $z > 1$, before being replaced by dry mergers at $z < 1$ (e.g. Webb+15, McDonald+16)?
- Understanding the relationship between BCGs and their host clusters requires large, uniformly-selected samples.
- We use the XXL 100 brightest cluster sample (Pacaud+16).

The XXL 100 brightest cluster sample:

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BCG identification:

- Brightest galaxy in the z-band
- within $0.5 \times r_{500}$ of the X-ray centroid
- with a redshift consistent with that of the cluster as determined from all redshifts within $0.5 \times r_{500}$ of the cluster, i.e.
- $|z_{\text{gal}} - z_{\text{cl}}| < \sigma_z (1 + z_{\text{cl}})$, with $\sigma_z = 0.04 - 0.065$.
- Visual inspection confirms a sensible BCG choice in 90% of cases, in the remaining 10% of cases the photo-z condition is dropped.
- 15 clusters are excluded due to foreground contamination, lack of photometry/spectroscopy, AGN contamination in X-ray.
- **Final sample of 85 clusters + BCGs**, 45 in XXL-N, 40 in XXL-S.
- Measurements include BCG offset, c_{SB} , $M_{500\text{WL}}$, M_{BCG}^* , BCG *griz*

Measures of cluster relaxation: BCG offset

- X-ray emitting gas traces the cluster potential.
- BCG offset can be used to indicate relaxation state.
- Offsets consistent with HIFLUGCS once the XMM centroid uncertainty is taken into account.

Measures of cluster relaxation: X-ray gas concentration

- c_{SB} measures the surface brightness concentration (Santos +2008).
- XXL c_{SB} values taken from Democles+2017 (in prep.).
- Tests using simulated cluster images indicates that c_{SB} is accurate (0.02) with a scatter of 0.13.

Computing BCG stellar mass:

- Computing BCG stellar masses requires knowledge of the star formation history (SFH).
- Following Lidman+12, we deduce an average SFH for the BCG sample.
- CFHTLS-W1 photometry in XXL-N is deeper and we model the SFH using i - z BCG colours in this field.
- Charlot & Bruzual 07 model, Salpeter IMF, $Z=Z_{\odot}$, SSP, $z_f=2.5$.
- Resulting z -band stellar mass uncertainties are 10-20%, dominated by the model uncertainties.
- Compare to Lidman+12 errors of 5-10% yet excluding model uncertainties.

Computing BCG stellar mass:

Star formation in BCGs:

- A subset of 30 BCGs at $z < 0.5$ with SDSS DR12 spectroscopy show very low H α -determined SFR levels.
- Low colour offsets between BCGs and stacked red sequence fits consistent with SSP models with $\tau < 1$ Gyr.
- SFR levels consistent with field ellipticals of similar mass and redshift.
- XXL-100 BCGs appear to be uniformly passive irrespective of host cluster relaxation state.

Cluster weak lensing mass versus BCG stellar mass relation:

- More massive BCGs exist in more massive clusters.
- The relationship between cluster and BCG mass may be expressed as a power-law of the form **$M_{\text{cluster}} = A \times M_{\text{BCG}}^n$**
- Cluster weak lensing masses are taken from Lieu+16.
- We classify relaxed clusters as those displaying BCG offsets $< 0.05 r_{500}$, fitting relaxed/unrelaxed systems separately.
- We further investigate weighting the sample by c_{SB} and $(c_{\text{SB}})^{-1}$ to highlight relaxed/unrelaxed clusters.

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Case	n	$\log A$	#
All clusters	0.84 ± 0.09	4.33	85
c_{SB} weighted	1.04 ± 0.24	1.79	–
$(c_{\text{SB}})^{-1}$ weighted	0.55 ± 0.16	7.89	–
BCG offset $< 0.05 \times r_{500}$	1.03 ± 0.10	1.97	55
BCG offset $> 0.05 \times r_{500}$	0.46 ± 0.17	8.88	30

BCGs in relaxed clusters follow a linear stellar mass versus cluster weak lensing mass relation, with approximately 1-3% of the cluster total mass existing as stars in the BCG.

Cartoon view: Snapshots of BCG-cluster evolution

- Immediately following a cluster merger event the cluster total mass increases yet the BCG stellar mass lags relative to the new cluster mass (A-B).
- As the cluster relaxes, the BCG and other bright (massive) galaxies migrate to the cluster centre via dynamical friction where they merge, increasing the BCG stellar mass (B-C).
- Absence of SF points to dry mergers as the dominant route to stellar mass growth.

Additional notes: Luminosity segregation

- Bright galaxies are more centrally concentrated than faint.
- Bright galaxies in relaxed clusters are more centrally concentrated than in unrelaxed clusters.
- Bright galaxies preferentially migrate to the cluster centre via dynamical friction and do so to a greater extent in relaxed systems.

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